

Special Relativity Based on Frames, but Also Vector and Scalar Interaction Quantities

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Special relativity may be thought of in terms of viewing a system at rest from a frame moving at a constant v , using the well-known relation $x=vt$. This relation guarantees that x and x' (x -value seen in the moving frame) cannot be the same, but does not give an a priori reason for transforming t or the rest mass, m_0 , via a single Lorentz matrix we argue. In (1), we argued that Newtonian scalar kinetic energy and vector momentum provided the incentive for creating a matrix that transformed $m_0 c c$ (such that explicit Newtonian results $m_0 c c + .5 m v v$ and $p=m_0 v$, m_0 =rest mass, arise in the $v \ll c$ limit).

Here we argue that one may obtain the notion of vector $dp = \text{Integral } F dt$ and scalar $ke = \text{Integral } F \cdot v dt$ in Newtonian mechanics with no explicit form for these two quantities and then suggest that a frame view should apply to both x, t and the scalar and vector interaction quantities. The only scalar quantity in a rest frame seems to be the rest mass and so we suggest that one may introduce a single matrix (Lorentz matrix) and apply it to $(0, m_0 c c)$ and (x, ct) . In such a case, it is seen that t must change as seen in the moving frame.

Newtonian Mechanics and Special Relativity

In (1), we used explicit forms from Newtonian mechanics:

$$p=m_0 v \text{ (one dimension) and } ke = .5 m_0 v v \text{ ((1))}$$

and noted that $x=vt$ is of the same form as $p=m_0 v$ if p is linked with the vector x and t with the scalar $m_0 c c$ such that full energy is $m_0 c c + .5 m_0 v v$ in the Newtonian case. This suggested that x, t and $p, m_0 c c$ were on the same footing and allowed for the creation of a 2×2 transformation matrix (Lorentz matrix). Here we wish to be more general and not use the explicit forms ((1)).

Special Relativity for (x, ct) Alone

Given $x=vt$ ((2)) and the idea that a rest mass m_0 at $x=0$ at t is seen as an object moving at v from a frame moving at $-v$, we note that if $x=0, t=0$ and $x'=0, t'=0$ are origin points in both frames, that one may see that:

$$X' = g(v) v t \text{ ((3)) where } x' \text{ is measured in the moving frame.}$$

Here $g(v)$ is an unknown function. One might at first consider $g(v) = 1$ and argue that t does not transform to t' , but x' must change from x . If one decides to be more general and consider $t'=g(v) t$ one may introduce a 2×2 matrix:

$$\begin{bmatrix} g(v) & v g(v) \\ v g(v) & g(v) \end{bmatrix} \text{ ((4))}$$

One may seek a conserved modulus, but cannot use $x'^2 + c^2 t'^2 = x^2 + c^2 t^2$ as: $x=0$, $x' = v g(v)t$ and $t' = g(v)t$. In such a case;

$$c^2 t g(v) g(v) (v v / c^2 + 1) = c^2 t^2 \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{One would have: } g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1 + v v / c^2} \quad ((6))$$

In such a case, a $\Delta t = t - 0$ as seen in the rest frame would be $t/\sqrt{1 + v v / c^2} < t$ which contradicts muon decay times for fast moving muons. Thus, one should use a minus in ((5)), i.e.

$$g(v) = 1/\sqrt{1 - v v / c^2} \quad ((7))$$

One may make alternative arguments for the minus using momentum-energy considerations, but in this section we assume no knowledge of the existence of momentum or energy.

Newtonian Interaction Considerations

We begin by assuming no knowledge of the concepts of energy or momentum in Newtonian mechanics. We then argue that one may consider a rapid hit to a piece of glass which breaks it. The key physical idea is that the hit may be represented by a vector with a finite magnitude and that dt must be tiny. We then consider this vector hit acting on a rest mass m_0 . It will give the mass m_0 a velocity v , but this occurs in an infinitesimal amount of time. Thus, we postulate two vector quantities:

$$dp/dt = F \quad \text{where } F \text{ is a vector measure of the hit and } p(m_0, v) \text{ linked to both the mass and velocity of the particle} \quad ((8))$$

At this point, the exact form of p vector is completely unknown. It is, however, linked with a physical property of the particle as such a particle with p may go on to break the glass instead of F breaking it directly. One may also define a scalar

$$F \cdot dr = F \cdot v \, dt \quad \text{where } v = dr/dt \text{ vector} \quad ((9))$$

One may see that $F \cdot dr$ is a scalar and differs from the magnitude of $F \cdot dt$. We thus suggest that if one has a moving object, it will be associated with both a scalar ((9)) and a vector p .

Frame Considerations

We have noted above that a particle at rest at $x=0$, t is seen to move with v from a frame moving with $-v$. This means that there should exist a scalar and vector in the moving frame. In the rest frame there would be no vector as there is no motion, but a scalar and vector cannot emerge from nothing and so we suggest the presence of a scalar in the rest frame which becomes a scalar and a vector as seen in the moving frame. Furthermore, the transformation

((4)) which was used for x, ct with the guess that t should transform may now be used with confidence because ((9)) shows that a scalar in the rest frame must change when seen from the moving frame even if one is not convinced that t should change. Both x, ct and a scalar in the rest frame should transform via the 2×2 matrix ((4)). Given $x=vt$, one has the explicit form of ((4)) and sees that if $m_0 c^2$ is taken as the scalar, as there is no other scalar in the rest frame, then p is proportional to v . One does not have to be aware of the Newtonian form $p=mv$ a priori. Furthermore, in calculating an invariant modulus using $m_0 c^2$ in the rest frame and E, p in the moving frame, given that $E > m_0 c^2$ and $[p] > 0$, one must use a minus metric (without knowing about muon decay times).

We argue that in order to obtain the full form of energy and momentum, one must be aware of these physical interaction scalar and vector quantities by a physical consideration of the interaction required to bring about motion of an object, the very motion seen by a person in a moving frame. One cannot simply ignore interaction features when using the frame of reference approach, otherwise there would be no physical reason for transforming $(0, m_0 c^2)$ in the first place, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that given muon decay rates decreasing for very fast moving muons, one could in principle derive special relativistic equations for x, t in the rest frame and x', t' as seen by a moving frame, but there would be no concept of momentum and energy based on the frame approach. (In other words, these notions were first introduced by Newton.) We suggest that even if one did not know Newton's kinetic energy and momentum expression, one could postulate the equation $F=dp/dt$ based on the following ideas. Given a piece of glass, one may break it by a very swift hit. One cannot break the hit into tiny hit pieces and apply each in a tiny time, an overall tiny time and a large hit are required. One may next apply such a hit F and tiny time dt to a particle with rest mass m_0 . It may then go on to break the glass. Thus, we suggest that a non-moving particle has a vector $p=0$ quantity which becomes p vector in a very tiny dt , or dp/dt and we set this equal to a vector F which is presumably proportional to the hit strength. We then define a scalar quantity $F \cdot dr = F \cdot v dt$ which is not of the same value as the magnitude of $F dt$. We suggest that there should exist both a scalar and vector related to interaction and if one uses a relative frame picture and sees a particle moving from the moving frame, then the scalar and vector should appear, but only a scalar should be present in the rest frame, as a vector and scalar cannot emerge from nothing and $p=0$ for no motion. The only scalar in the rest frame is rest mass and so we argue that one may use the matrix for x, ct and apply it to $(0, m_0 c^2)$. One may then create an invariant modulus using a -1 metric without knowing about muon decay rates because $m_0 c^2$ in the rest frame cannot be linked to the sum of two bigger numbers E' and magnitude of p' . A minus is needed in the modulus: $-m_0 c^2 = -E^2 + p \cdot p c^2$.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. The Importance of Newtonian KE and P on Special Relativity (preprint, zenodo, 2026)